

Color Piercing of the Head and Hind Legs of Rabbits

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Abstract: The pathological state of rabbit teeth is very common in clinical practice and can cause complications that can lead to death. Therefore, special attention should be paid to early diagnosis in order to find out in time. X-ray diagnosis is reflected in X-ray examination to evaluate the condition. A method of interpreting X-ray images, comparing the characteristics of other animal species.

Keywords: Radiography, assessment, prognosis, stage. lateral projection.

INTRODUCTION. In daily practice, in order to carry out X-ray examination of rabbits in the lateral projection, the animal should be placed in a lateral lying position, the dorsal part of the head is slightly raised from the table and placed parallel to the sagittal plane. It should be directed from the center to the level of X-rays. It is important that the left and right sides of the head are symmetrical on the X-ray (Symmetry is assumed based on the sum of the orbital edges). There are many radiographs (radiographs) of rabbits with left angular processes and right sides, as well as left and right ventral contours, which we use to diagnose sick rabbits.

X-ray phase contrast imaging has the potential to revolutionize the study of physiology and internal biomechanics in small animals. It is the only commonly used technique that has the necessary spatial and temporal resolutions, punctuation power, and soft tissue sensitivity required to visualize the internal physiology of living animals at the millimeter to micron scale.

Figure 1. Roentgenogram of the skull of a rabbit (side view of the rabbit's mouth).

The normal X-ray anatomy of the skull in clinically healthy animals is consistent and parallel without changes in tooth structure. It is taken from the tip of the hard palate to the soft palate, equal to one third of its height.

In this type of animal, the teeth erupt from five lower jaws and teeth and cheek teeth. In addition, the mandibular cheek tips should not enter the ventral mandibular groove.

Ventral cuspid recusps adjacent to cusps of equal thickness below the first three cheek teeth indicate retrograde elongation of the tooth.

The greater the intraoral level, the less obvious the tooth elongation. Upper and lower jaw teeth are formed by four each. Cheek teeth, upper and lower jaws match each other.

Inconsistency in length is an indicator of this type of dental problems. In the skull, the upper jaw goes from the edge of the tooth to the edge.

The most caudo-lateral part of the ipsilateral mandible is the level of the temporal zygomatic process located in the lower part.

Rabbits' teeth protrude only beyond the radiolucent apical (front molar) line of the first molar of the upper jaw without significant elongation. If they catch on something or become trapped, they can protrude and cause bone fractures.

In most cases, a tire or heavy object will suffice. After a complete physical examination and stabilization, radiographs were taken, sometimes surgery is necessary because this rabbit has a transverse femur (thigh bone) fracture (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. Roentgenogram of the hind leg of a rabbit

The animal should be placed in a lateral recumbent position, the dorsal part of the head is slightly raised from the table, and the sagittal plane is placed parallel to the cassette.

Central x-rays should be directed to the level of premolars and molars (the left and right sides are very important, the head is symmetrical on the radiograph). Symmetry is estimated based on the sum of the rostral edges of the orbit, the optic foramina, the mandibular coronoid, and the angular processes of the left and right sides, as well as left and right ventrally. our use of radiography to put.

The conclusion. In this ban, the bones of the skull and hind legs of the rabbits were pierced with the help of roentgenogram because the examination of the skull is a simple, quick and inevitable procedure to evaluate the condition of the teeth. Nevertheless, the research was conducted based on the study of the specific features reflected in the X-ray examination of the rabbit's teeth. The study of the hind leg bone pathology.

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